

EFFECTS OF THE INTERFACE ON LOCAL VERSUS GLOBAL LOAD SHARING BEHAVIOR IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER LONGITUDINAL TENSION

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SUMMARY: The effects of interfaces on load sharing behavior was evaluated by performing single-fiber and multiple-fiber single-ply fragmentation experiments and analysis of SiC/Ti-6Al-4V composites at room temperature. Fiber breaks were monitored by acoustic emission sensors, and the break locations were determined using a novel ultrasonic shear wave back reflection (SBR) technique. Data analysis was performed using Curtin's fragmentation model. High friction stresses were obtained under fragmentation conditions (e.g., 390 MPa for SCS-6 fibers) and were consistent with lack of any significant length of shear crack at the interface. Mechanical data and microstructural observations confirmed local load sharing (LLS) even for "weak" interfaces, and the mechanism is illustrated. The strengths of single-ply composites with different interfaces were predicted extremely well by Zweben and Rosen's LLS model, using a stress concentration factor that was derived based on a simple plasticity model of load transfer.

KEYWORDS : Interface, longitudinal, metal matrix composites, titanium, silicon carbide, Load sharing, fragmentation, single-fiber, local, global, damage, plasticity, slip

INTRODUCTION

The anisotropic nature of fiber reinforced composites necessitates the optimization of interface properties. Thus, the requirement of a strong interface for adequate transverse (90°) strength and creep resistance is at variance to the conventional wisdom of a weak interface for longitudinal strength. A recent review article [1] sheds insight into the issues involved for metal matrix composites. In this paper, the mechanisms by which interface properties influence the longitudinal strength in titanium matrix composites (TMCs), are explored.

In the absence of a matrix crack, the interface becomes important only in the presence of a fiber break. Fairly high shear and compressive radial stresses are generated at the interface next to the break [2-4], and the former can be sufficient to cause interface shear failure and relative fiber-matrix sliding. The sliding resistance at the interface is usually represented by an effective frictional sliding stress, τ . The prevailing understanding is that when τ is high, there is high elastic stress concentration in the adjacent fiber to cause it to fail in a cooperative

or cumulative manner. The ensuing sequence of fiber fractures, implicitly assumed to be coplanar, can lead to failure of the composite. This mechanism is termed local load sharing (LLS). When τ is small, the elastic stress concentration is less due to the longer debond length, and may not induce failure of the adjacent fiber. Consequently, fiber fractures can accumulate at random sites, and this mode of progressive fiber failure is termed global load sharing (GLS). Composite strength models have been developed for both GLS [5,6] and LLS [7,8] modes of fiber fractures. GLS provides higher composite strength and also has the advantage that the strength is not dependent on the volume of the composite, which is important when considering large structures.

The exact role of the interface on load sharing behavior was recently quantified in [9], based on the ratio of the stress concentration in nearest and next nearest neighbors. For a 35 volume percent SiC/Ti-alloy TMC, the model indicates that GLS would occur when τ was less than about 10% of the fiber strength. Using available data on interface friction stress from push-out tests and extracted fiber strength, this implies that GLS would prevail at room temperature for most composites of interest. On the other hand, except for reference [10] where there are concerns regarding the analysis used, available strength data and fiber break density and locations in a number of TMCs [11,12] suggest that LLS is the dominant mechanism. At the load at which the first fiber fails randomly, the stresses in all fibers are quite high, so that even small stress concentrations can set up successive failures of both nearest and next-nearest neighbors. Also, plasticity from a fiber break can produce significant stress concentration and lead to LLS, as will be demonstrated in this paper.

Past experimental efforts for evaluating the influence of the interface on longitudinal properties have typically relied on heat treatments of a composite [13,14], such that the interface is altered by adverse fiber-matrix reactions. Such reactions serve to change (increase) the fiber-matrix bond strength and frictional resistance, which is required for a comparative study, but which have the undesirable consequence of significantly degrading both fiber and the matrix properties. Consequently, strength loss of the composite cannot simply be ascribed to changes in interface conditions and load sharing behavior. This work differs from previous efforts in that attention was focused on the mechanisms of progressive fiber failures at the micro and meso scales, rather than on a macroscopic parameter such as the composite strength. Attention was confined to composites with only limited number of fibers, in single-fiber and multiple-fiber single-ply configurations. In particular, the single-fiber experiments and analysis methodology [15,16] were used to characterize the interface under fragmentation conditions, and to subsequently use that data to evaluate fiber failures in multiple-fiber specimens. The interface was varied by selecting SiC fibers with different coatings, and associated different interface properties. This overall approach using mini/micro-composites is part of our continuing effort at establishing a comprehensive methodology for developing optimized interfaces in TMCs.

EXPERIMENTS

Single-fiber and multi-fiber single-ply specimens were fabricated by hot pressing SiC fibers between two Ti-6Al-4V sheets at 950°C. Tensile specimens with a 25.4 mm gage length x 15.2 mm width x 0.7 mm thickness were prepared by electric discharge machining. Three different fibers were considered: (i) SCS-0 fiber, which is a 140 μm diameter uncoated SiC fibers from Textron Specialty Metals (TSM), (ii) SCS-6 fiber, which is essentially the SCS-0 fiber coated with turbostatic carbon (graphitic) with graded amounts of Si, and (iii) Trimarc

fiber, which is a 125 μm diameter SiC fiber from ARC Amercom, with a "soft-hard-soft" turbostatic carbon coating. These fibers were selected because the interfaces represent a rather wide range of interface tensile (normal) strength [17-19] and frictional push-out stresses (see Table 1), so that the influence of the interface on load sharing behavior can be assessed. Multiple fiber specimens were prepared in two different configurations. One was a 15-fiber specimen with a 0.7 mm fiber spacing, and was used primarily to understand the basic deformation mechanisms. The other multiple-fiber configuration was a 40-fiber specimen with a center-to-center fiber spacing of 200 μm , that is characteristic of typical 30 volume percent TMCs. These 40-fiber samples had smaller specimen dimensions, with a fiber volume percent of approximately 11.6 for the SCS-6 and SCS-0 fibers, and approximately 9 for the Trimarc fibers. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature (RT), and acoustic emission (AE) sensors were used to detect fiber breaks. The break locations were determined using an ultrasonic shear wave back reflection (SBR) technique [20-22], and those results correlated extremely well with the break locations determined metallographically.

Table 1: Interface and Fiber Strength Data for the SiC/Ti-6Al-4V Systems

Fiber	Extracted Fiber, σ_o , (Lo=25.4 mm) MPa	Extracted Fiber Weibull modulus, m	Push-Out frictional stress, τ , MPa	Normal (Tensile) Interface Strength, MPa	Fragmentation strength, σ_o , Mpa (Lo = 25.4mm)	Fragmentation Weibull modulus, m	Fragmentation friction stress, τ , MPa
SCS-6	4480	14	160-190 ¹	100-120	3300	5	390
Trimarc	3400	20	30 ²	~ 0-20	3050	9	190
SCS-0	1500	6	290-320 ¹	~ 380	1300	6	500

¹ Debond stress, τ_d , corresponding to the maximum load before the load drop, since the load increased rapidly after the load drop. ² Sliding stress in the constant load region following debonding.

DATA ANALYSIS

Past research in single-fiber fragmentation (SFF) testing has relied primarily on the well-known Kelly-Tyson equation [23]: $\tau = (\sigma_f r)/L_c$, where L_c is the critical length of fibers at break saturation, and σ_f is the fiber strength. Since fiber strengths generally follow Weibull statistics, this requires an independent measurement of fiber strengths. Also, the procedure assumes that the insitu strength of the fibers in the composite remain the same as when fibers are tested independently, an assumption that may be violated in TMCs. In addition, the formula does not provide a methodology to assess stress concentration effects and load sharing in multiple fiber samples. After surveying a number of recent models [24,25], the analytical fiber fragmentation model of Curtin [26] was selected for assessing the fragmentation data. We also performed Monte Carlo simulation of the fragmentation experiment, and found excellent correlation with Curtin's model. The three parameters that emerge from the analysis are: the insitu Weibull modulus (m) and Weibull strength (σ_o) of the fiber, and the shear stress, τ , at the interface under fiber-fracture conditions. The details of the application of the model in experiments are described in [15]. Essentially, two plots are obtained from the fragmentation test: (i) the stress plot, which contains the probability ($\text{LnLn}\{1/(1-P_f)\}$) of fiber breaks plotted versus the logarithm of the applied stress, and (ii) cumulative number of breaks plotted versus the fragment length; here P_f is the fiber failure

probability. The analysis involves selection the three parameters that best match the two experimental plots. Among them , m is the simplest to evaluate, since it represents the slope of the stress plot. Also, if $\log(N)$ is plotted versus $\log(\text{stress})$, the curve is linear in the initial stages with a slope close to m (see additional details in [15]); here N is the cumulative number of fiber breaks. Comparison of single and multiple fiber results provide a means of evaluating whether stress concentration effects are operative.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows SBR scans for the single fiber specimens. The location of breaks are indicated by the short white line (only a two are marked for the Trimarc fiber). From such scans and the stress-strain-AE data, the stress and fragment length plots were obtained.

Fig. 1: SBR images for the single fiber specimens: (a) SCS-6 fiber, (b) Trimarc fiber.

Fig. 2: (a) Weibull stress plot for the single-fiber Trimarc/Ti-6Al-4V sample
(b) Corresponding fragment length distribution plot

Figs. 2a and 2b illustrate the results for the Trimarc/Ti-6Al-4V system. Referring to Fig. 2a, it may be noted that the fiber stress was determined by multiplying the measured strain by the fiber modulus and then subtracting the residual stress in the fiber. This assumes isostrain conditions, which is violated when substantial gaps develop between the ends of the broken fiber. The deviation of the data from the theoretical curve in Fig. 2a is believed to arise from this effect. Hence, only the initial part of the theoretical curve was used to match with the data in Fig. 2a. The second point to note is that the axial compressive residual stress in the fiber was determined by an etching technique to lie between 600 and 900 MPa for both the

single and multiple-fiber specimens. This is well below that based on the assumption of a stress-free fiber at the processing temperature, and is believed to be due to loading of the fiber at the processing temperature (because of the very small amount of fibers).

Using plots such as Fig. 2, the insitu Weibull strength, σ_0 , the Weibull modulus, m , and the frictional sliding stress, τ , were determined. They are listed in the last three columns of Table 1, where σ_0 is determined at the gage length $L_0=25.4$ mm. The table also contains data from tensile tests on extracted fibers, frictional stress from push-out tests, and the tensile (normal) strength measured by using the cruciform specimen geometry [17-19].

A common feature of the data in Table 1 is the significantly higher friction stress obtained from the fragmentation experiment compared with the push-out test. For example, in the case of the Trimarc fiber, the fragmentation frictional stress is nearly six times that obtained from push-out tests. In the case of SCS-6 fibers, the frictional sliding stress determined from the fragmentation experiments is 390 MPa, compared with only 160-190 MPa obtained from push-out tests; the latter is slightly higher than reported values for a 30 volume percent SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V composite [27]. These high friction stresses under fragmentation conditions suggest that there may be significant clamping of the fiber at the fiber break, which may prevent propagation of the interface crack. If a friction coefficient of 0.5 is assumed for the SCS-6 fiber (based on push-out tests), it implies that in the fragmentation test there is a radial clamping on the fiber of 780 MPa, which is of the order of the yield stress of the matrix, approximately 850 MPa. The analysis in [2,3] suggest that this level of stress can indeed be generated in the proximity of the break. A more recent elastic-plastic analysis [4] indicates that even if a small split was assumed along the interface (representative of a debond crack), the local radial stress at the tip of that crack is negative and singular, suggesting that it would always be very difficult to propagate the interface debond crack under fragmentation conditions.

Fig. 3 illustrates the interface region next to a fiber break in a SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V specimen.

Fig. 3: Micrograph showing coating damage near a fiber break in a SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V sample.

Fig. 4: Cumulative number of breaks versus the stress for the single and 15-fiber Trimarc composite. The predictions for 25.4 mm length and 381 mm length are indicated

Although Fig. 3 illustrates a number of damage features, such as transverse cracks approaching the fiber from the cracked reaction zone, or isolated interface cracks very close to the SiC surface, there is very little evidence of a continuous shear crack along the interface. While it is indeed very difficult to verify shear cracks in such carbonaceous coatings, the observations so far suggest that shear interface failure is extremely limited, which is consistent with the high frictional shear stress evaluated from the mechanical data.

Fig. 4 is a stress plot for a 15-fiber Trimarc/Ti-6Al-4V specimen, where $\ln(N)$ is plotted versus the logarithm of the breaking stress, $\ln(\sigma)$. This method of plotting is necessary because the specimen cannot be taken to fiber fracture saturation. Fig. 4 includes data from the SFF tests, as well as the theoretical curve for a gage length of 25.4 mm, using parameters that were determined earlier, i.e., $\sigma_0=3050$ MPa, $m=9$, and $\tau=190$ MPa; the designation in the plot is 3050-9-190. Also included in Fig. 4 is the theoretical curve for the same set of parameters, but for a total fiber length of 381 mm, which is the total length available for fracture in the 15-fiber/25.4 mm gage-length specimen. The basis for this latter curve is that it represents the failure stress distribution if there was no interaction between the 15 fibers. Thus, any interaction between neighboring fibers would manifest in the form of a lack of agreement with the theoretical 15-fiber curve.

Fig. 4 shows that although the 15-fiber specimen approached the theoretical curve at higher stresses, the experimental data significantly deviated from the 15-fiber theoretical curve at lower values of stresses. During the initial stage, when fiber strain is well represented by the measured strain, the slope for the experimental data is higher than the theoretical slope by about a factor of 2. Since the slope of the curve represents the Weibull modulus, the 15-fiber data suggests a higher apparent Weibull modulus for the fibers. Since there is no reason why the insitu fiber statistics should differ from the SFF samples, the higher apparent Weibull modulus may be interpreted as being due to a stress-concentration effect between neighboring fibers. This is because the occurrence of a break under stress concentration conditions would quickly load up fibers in adjacent locations, thus setting up a succession of breaks with very little increase required in the applied stress/strain. In essence, this would manifest as a higher Weibull modulus.

Fig. 5:(a) Face of the 15-fiber Trimarc specimen showing macroscopic slip bands on the specimen face. (b) SBR image, illustrating that the intersection of bands with the fiber correspond to the fiber break locations.

Figs. 5a and 5b correspond to the 15-fiber specimen whose data were plotted in Fig. 4. Fig. 5a is a macroscopic view of the specimen face and shows a criss-cross pattern of slip bands that are concentrated in a relatively small section of the gage length. Figure 5b illustrates the fiber break locations, as imaged by the SBR technique, and shows a one-to-one correspondence between the slip band intersections with the fiber and the fiber break locations. The intense but macroscopic slip bands are not observed in the unreinforced material, nor can they be seen near the specimen edges in Fig. 5a because the fibers are located a small distance away from the edges. Together, Figs. 5a and 5b indicate that fiber fractures have occurred cooperatively, with localized matrix plasticity being responsible for cumulative failure of fibers. This type of LLS behavior is consistent with the higher Weibull modulus for the 15-fiber specimen compared with the single fiber specimen (see Fig. 4).

Interrupted tests, where specimens were periodically unloaded to obtain SBR and plasticity images [15], have confirmed that fiber fractures are strongly influenced by slip bands which propagate from a fiber break and impinge on the neighboring fiber. Note that the LLS behavior that is observed is not inconsistent with the results in [9], since that model predicts that LLS will always occur in single-ply composites. However, the mechanism of stress concentration is different here, and needs to be modeled rigorously.

In order to illustrate how these results translate to higher volume fraction composites, Fig. 6 is presented for the 40-fiber specimens that had a center-to-center fiber distance of 200 μm . The stress-strain curve for the Ti-6Al-4V matrix is also plotted here.

Fig. 6: Stress-strain curves for the 40-fiber single-ply composites and the neat Ti-6Al-4V matrix.

In this figure, point D corresponds to failure of the SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V specimen, and point A corresponds to an instability point in the Trimarc/Ti-6Al-4V specimen. For the latter specimen, instability ended at point B, and the specimen was subsequently unloaded at point C, by which time the crack in the specimen had almost fully propagated through the specimen width. The SCS-0/Ti-6Al-4V specimen exhibited a constant flow stress well below that of the matrix, and it was unloaded at approximately 1% strain. The stress-strain curve for the SCS-0 case became non-linear at approximately 0.5 % strain, which was substantially lower than the flow stress of the Ti-6Al-4V matrix. Additional important parameters about the data are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Tensile Data and Predictions for the 40-Fiber Single-Ply Specimens

Type of Fiber	Vol. % Fibers	Yield Strain %	Measured Tensile Strength, MPa	Measured Flow Stress, MPa	Predicted Strength Using Zweben's LLS Model, MPa	Predicted Strength Using Curtin's GLS Model, MPa
SCS-6	11.6	0.66	1160	-	1180	1207
SCS-0	11.6	0.5	-	732	725 ¹	1020
Trimarc	9	0.695	1076		1064	1096

¹ For the SCS-0 fibers, the strain at non-linearity is more relevant than the final flow stress. The non-linearity was observed at approx. 0.5%, and was well predicted by the LLS model.

The most revealing aspect of the above specimens is obtained from optical observation and SBR images. Fig. 7 shows the face of the specimens, wherein it may be observed that an intense slip band has traversed the entire width of the specimen for the SCS-6 and Trimarc fibers, both of which possess relatively weak interfaces. Final fracture took place inside these intense slip zones, and SBR images showed that the fibers were severely fragmented within the zone. No fiber fractures are determined outside the band, consistent with slip not being observed at other locations, as well as lack of any significant AE event prior to specimen fracture. The fiber failure locations confirm LLS in these materials with relatively weak interfaces. The specimen with SCS-0 fibers shows a rather unanticipated behavior, in that the entire gage length is filled with a criss-cross arrangement of localized slip, presumably connecting regions of severely fragmented fibers.

DISCUSSION

The fragmentation experiments and analysis show that useful data can be extracted from the single-fiber fragmentation test, and that the analysis can be used to assess load sharing behavior in multiple-fiber specimens. Thus, local load sharing manifests as a higher insitu Weibull modulus for the multiple fiber specimen compared with the single fiber sample.

Fig. 7: Macroscopic slip traces on the faces of the 40-fiber specimens. (a) and (b) show that fracture was contained inside the intense slip band that traversed the width of the SCS-6 and Trimarc fiber specimens. Fig. 7(c) shows a criss-cross arrangement of slip bands in the entire gage section of the sample with SCS-0 fibers.

The tests show that the friction stress is much higher under fragmentation conditions than in a push-out test, and this is believed to be due to substantial clamping of the fiber at the location of the break. The microstructures also showed very little evidence of debonding. The high friction stresses are a real effect, and indicate that shear stresses obtained from push-out tests are not applicable when considering fiber failures in longitudinal loaded composites.

A more difficult item to resolve is the discrepancy in the Weibull parameters (see Table 1) obtained from the fragmentation tests versus those obtained by testing extracted fibers, although the difference is modest for the SCS-0 and Trimarc fibers. The worst agreement is for the SCS-6 fibers, and a possible reason is damage to the fibers during testing. This is discussed in more detail in [15] and is based on the SCS-6 coating structure [28]. It may be noted that the SCS-6 fiber has been found to exhibit strength degradation under fatigue crack growth conditions [29-31], whereas Trimarc fibers do not show that behavior [29]. Thus, SCS-6 fibers appear to be more prone to damage than the Trimarc fibers, and explanation may lie in the interlayer next to the SiC surface and the profile of that surface.

As final part of the discussion, we shall attempt to rationalize the strengths obtained from the 40-fiber specimens. In a previous paper [11], we have shown the existence of LLS at RT in a 4-ply SCS-6/Ti-25Al-17V composite. The evidence was based on significant strength over-prediction by Curtin's GLS model [6], and lack of random fiber breaks outside a thin 2 mm band on either side of the fracture surface. It was found [11] that Zweben and Rosen's LLS model [7], based on the occurrence of the second fiber break, provided excellent correlation with the measured strengths. In this model, the critical event is the formation of a doublet, where the second break is due to stress concentration from the first break.

In reference [11], a stress concentration factor of 1.146 was assumed, based on the elastic calculations in [32]. On the other hand, the current observations suggest the scenario shown in Figure 8, where slip bands emanating from the break allow the high modulus fibers to pick up the load at four equivalent locations, making those locations vulnerable to fracture. Since

the load is equally transmitted along the slip bands, at most one fourth of the load in the center fiber is picked up at any one location by the unbroken high modulus fiber. In other words, as a first approximation we obtain a stress concentration factor of 1.25 at the possible fiber fracture location, although this needs to be confirmed by rigorous analysis. The strength prediction follows from the following equation for the fiber stress, σ_f [7,11]:

$$\{\delta \cdot L / L_0^2\} \cdot N_t \cdot C \cdot (\sigma_f / \sigma_0)^{2m} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where δ is the shear lag distance ($= \sigma_f d / 4\tau$), d is the fiber diameter, L_0 is the length on which σ_0 is based, L is the gage length of the sample, N_t is the total number of fibers, and C is a constant, given by $C = 4 \cdot \{k^m - 1\}$, where k is the stress concentration factor, and is assessed to be 1.25 for the single-ply specimens. Substituting in $\sigma_c = v_f \cdot \sigma_f + (1 - v_f) \cdot \sigma_{matrix}$, and noting that σ_{matrix} is the matrix yield stress for the specimens with SCS-6 and Trimarc fibers, the composite strength, σ_c , can be obtained. Here v_f is the volume fraction of fibers. In the predictions, the friction stress was based on the fragmentation tests, and the Weibull parameters corresponded to those of the extracted fibers. The predicted strengths were 1180 MPa and 1064 MPa for the SCS-6 and Trimarc composites, respectively, which show excellent correlation with the corresponding measured values of 1160 MPa and 1076 MPa for these two materials (see Table 2). The corresponding GLS predictions using Curtin's model [6] are 1207 MPa and 1096 MPa, respectively. Although these numbers are also not very far from the measured strengths, the lack of random fiber breaks away from the intense slip zone suggests that the premise of the GLS model is violated in the current samples. In the case of the SCS-0 fibers, the second fiber break model leads to LLS becoming operative at a fiber stress of only 950 MPa (approx. 0.26%, using a fiber modulus of 370 GPa). Adding to this strain the residual strain (approx. 0.24%) in the fiber, the critical condition is predicted at an applied strain of 0.5 % strain, which also correlates extremely well with the experimental data (Fig.6). The constant flow stress for the sample with SCS-0 fibers is not predicted by the model, but the measured value is consistent with that of the yielded matrix modified by 11.6 percent of voided area.

Fig. 8. Sketch illustrating how a fiber break transmits load through local slip zones. The intersection of the lobes with the adjacent fibers are potential fiber failure sites.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A methodology has been established for extracting the interface friction stress and the insitu Weibull parameters from fragmentation tests. The friction stress is much higher under fragmentation conditions than in push-out tests, and the microstructures showed very little evidence of debonding.

2. The methodology is shown to be effective in assessing load sharing behavior in multi-fiber samples with different types of interfaces.
3. The results show that LLS is operative at room temperature even for interfaces that are considered to be relatively weak. Localized plasticity plays a dominant role in enhancing this load sharing mode in preference to GLS.
4. Strengths of composites with closely spaced fibers are very well predicted by a LLS model based on the second fiber break scenario. The model relies on a stress concentration factor of 1.25 for the single-ply material, and was derived based on a simple plasticity mechanism of load transfer.

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